

Parent as a Panopticon: Interrogating Notions of Power in *The Ordeal of Richard Feverel* and *Sons and Lovers*

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Abstract

Diverse notions of power have been heavily exploited by many post-colonial and postmodernist critics who tried to dismantle the power structures of the society but familial authority has never been questioned much. This research focuses upon implicit disparagement of the traditional role of parents and how in the name of care and love they snatch away their child's capacity to think for themselves. Although a major part of the paper would focus on George Meredith's *The Ordeal of Richard Feverel* and D.H Lawrence's *Sons and Lovers* where the former deals with a father-son relationship while the latter draws the relationship of a mother with her sons. This research will prove that the parent-child relationship is similar to a panopticon-prisoner model (metaphorically, not literally) by using Foucauldian and Orwellian strategies of surveillance in the novels. The ending will be preceded by an examination of the research by offering some solutions, stating its scopes, flaws and will be succeeded by some ambiguous questions.

Introduction

This study is qualitatively designed to analyse the notions of 'power' in a domestic panopticon, specifically focussing on the autocratic shades of parents in two intensively different ages of history. On the one hand, there is an overbearing father (Sir Austin in *The Ordeal of Richard Feverel*) and on the other side, we have an overprotective mother (Gertrude Morel in *Sons and Lovers*), both of them playing the role of a shield through the course of novels. Power has been defined by a number of theorists be it economic power which is equated with exploitation (Marxism), political power which takes the form of force (Totalitarianism), and familial power which is accorded a 'socializing role' because this is a 'soft-positive power' that must not be cross-questioned. Power has always been a weapon in the hands of a person who knows he/she is always right and who inherits the capacity to implement his/her power upon the weak. Parents try to cultivate all that is good for their child and the selfless role that they play in a child's life is unparalleled. But, at times their constant obsession with protecting their child ends in constructing a vulnerable being.

The concept of panopticon gained the interest of Bentham which he referred to as "the all-seeing place" specifically designed for surveillance towards the end of the eighteenth century (*Panopticon or the Inspection House*, 1791). These inspection houses were closely related to prisons and nothing more than that. Foucault in his *Discipline and Punish* (1979)

contrasted traditional powers with new technological sources of power which helped philosophers like Deleuze to theorize more on controlling societies (“Postscript on the societies of control” 1990). The term ‘panopticon’ might seem a bit antipathetic or negative for parents but the literal meaning of panopticon must be kept aside while reading this research work. Ignoring its mechanical and structural function, the study will try to locate parents as a panopticon who don’t keep a continuous check upon their children by using cameras but by inducing a hidden panopticon inside the minds of children i.e., rules and fear of breaking them. The upbringing of children is done according to the conventions of the family and parent’s outlook towards life which altogether shapes a child’s brain along with his way of thinking.

The very concept of power is very often associated with kings, queens, nobility, politicians, colonizers, bourgeoisie, celebrities, whites, men, and many more. But the origin of power lies silently in the institution of a family where parents act like a panopticon continuously looking at their children’s life (most probably adolescents). Just like proletariats, colonized, blacks and women have been a lot of times associated with the concept of ‘otherness’, similarly in an institution like family, some parents take the role of ‘powerful self’ while the children are tagged as ‘powerless others’ because they are supposed to remain silent and are expected to follow the norms of a family (prison) under the control of their parent (panopticon).

Family and its sovereign structures had always been partially if not wholly sketched by several writers since the medieval ages, but the concept received particular attention since the late 1900s. Foucauldian concept of the family being a foundational centre of power set the ground for interrogating or demobilizing an over-caring parent's traditional role. This study primarily focuses on paranoid parents who try to build a safe territory for their vulnerable children and the repercussions that follow. Additionally, the research proposes to examine the birth of domestic panopticon due to parents’ flawed marital relationships and presupposed fears that beget a constant craze of companionship from children.

Review of Literature

Talking about Meredith (1828-1909) and Lawrence (1885-1930), the former belongs to the Victorian Age while the latter belongs to a period of transition from Victorian to Modern. Despite the transition, their novels have provided us with two distinctively possessive parents of literature. Their novels are the primary texts of this study and are examples of Bildungsroman or Novel of Education. Though its obvious that such novels embody the

spiritual, psychological, and emotional development of children. Such is not the case with these novels generally for they mostly talk about hindrances and hurdles in the way of children's holistic development. Some research papers have talked about Mrs. Morel's disproportionate affection towards her sons and the consequences it entails which gave her the reputation of a "devouring mother," (Judith Ruderman) and few works have even given her the status of a 'narcissistic mother' (Rademacher). Previous research works on these novels dealt with its structure, themes of sexuality, gender politics, and significantly the study of unconscious but little has been researched upon by using the panopticon's concept. Even Orwellian perception of surveillance hasn't been applied in these two novels. Tobias Svensson has carried out a comparative study of *Nineteen Eighty-Four* and Upper Secondary School Students' perception of surveillance by using Michel Foucault's expansion of Jeremy Bentham's discussion of the Panopticon. That research solely focussed on juxtaposing two viewpoints i.e., Foucauldian 'panopticon' and Orwellian 'Big Brother is watching you' with respect to students' perception (Svensson 20).

An article published by Angela C. Henderson, Sandra M. Harmon, and Jeffery Houser namely "A New State of Surveillance? Applying Michel Foucault to Modern Motherhood" (2010) provided a base for further research on the concept of panopticon in the family system. Their article traced the journey of Philip Wylie's concept of "New Momism" (1942) where he defined momism as a way of mothering that characterized mothers who are "smothering, overprotective, and invested in their kids...[which] turned them into dysfunctional, snivelling weaklings, maternal slaves chained to the apron strings, unable to fight for their country or even stand on their own two feet" (Henderson 232). However, the article's major part focuses on mothers who suffer from pressure and surveillance due to various formal and informal settings but their research completely helped me in developing my own thoughts regarding domestic panopticon. Foucault's work on disciplinary punishment (*Discipline and Punishment, 1977*) targeted more at the social and psychological reality for prisoners that they are being constantly surveilled, and this is the approach I will take in the present study. Henderson says, "Prisoners already had a constant idea about their surveillance and due to this, they began to act as though they were being watched around the clock, even though the actual occurrence of surveillance was unverifiable. Constant surveillance induces a heightened self-awareness and paranoia among prisoners, which would in effect control their behaviour because of the perceived impending threat of being watched." (Henderson 235). The very same fear of being watched is experienced by

children of detective parents which eventually changes a child's social and emotional behaviour.

In Christopher Marlowe's *Tamburlaine the Great* (1590), the masculine protagonist (Tamburlaine) killed his cowardly son Calyphus for not becoming a copy of his robust father as he stayed back in his tents during the battle. Shakespeare's *Tempest* (1610-11) consisted of a passive daughter Miranda who is absolutely controlled by her father, Jonson's *Everyman out of his Humour* (1590) dealt with a detective father who not only protects his adolescent son from nasty peers but protects his self-conscience too while Austen's *Pride and Prejudice* (1813) incorporated a traditional mother whose excessive itch for marrying off her daughters took a grip of their emotional, social and cognitive growth. Stephen Spender's poem "My Parents" begins with the lines "My parents kept me from children who were rough, who threw words like stones and wore torn clothes" (lines 12) and readers are awed that how much caring his parents must be while ignoring the process of child's entry into a safe period of loneliness which made his life unsafe eventually. Literature has proved that we live in a society where an adult's journey to a non-existent celestial city (heaven) is appreciated (Christian in *The Pilgrim Progress*) but a child's journey in search of his personality always turns into a tragedy (Oliver in *Oliver Twist* and Munoo in *Coolie*). Golding's famous work *Lord of the Flies* has a character named Jack who says, "We are not savages We are English; We are best at everything" which provides an open space for postcolonial critics to talk about the binary opposition of 'English/self' and the 'Savages/other'. Similarly, parents also say, "We are not children. We are experienced; We are right if not best in whatever we think for you".

Nobody can deny that parents always work for the betterment of their children's growth but reproducing clones is no way less than the colonization of a mind. Several writers like Fanon and Ngũgĩ wa Thiong'o have written about the decolonization of mind and conscience in *The Wretched of the Earth* (1961) and *Decolonization of Mind* (1986) respectively but only to criticize colonizers. Family is the only powerful institution that can never be dethroned for it works like a charm. Just as tyrannic kings used to hand over their crown to their sons, similarly parents transmit the traditional norms of parenting to future generations without accepting the fact that a bad precedent shall never become a norm. Various cultural critics like T.S Eliot, Leavis, Adorno, and Horkheimer defined family as an 'adequate socializing agency' (Swingewood,13). Horkheimer's important study, *Authority of the Family* (1932-3) develops an argument that 'the psychic character of man' is determined by the stability or instability of major social institutions of which the family is pre-eminent (Swingewood 14). The concept of

parental authority has been exhaustively researched upon by Diana Baumrind who said, “An authority is a person whose expertness befits him to designate to the behavioural alternative where alternatives are perceived by both” (Baumrind 887). Some studies have also talked about wrongs done by excessive motherhood in some Swedish novels (Bjorklund) and the strong role of matriarchy in Victorian society (Reid). It is quite clear that all of the works mentioned till now, be it primary or secondary have provided an open space for further research on the concept of parental power. These works have constructed a metallic base for further exploration which can only remain lustrous if a researcher keeps on polishing the already existing pieces of writings.

Research Methodology

The research held concerning this dissertation was an applied one, but not new. Rather, numerous pieces of previous academic research exist regarding the role of ‘power’ in several social, cultural and political institutions. The concept of power has always been discussed by many theorists like Plato, Machiavelli, Nietzsche to Weber, Dahl, Marx, Judith Butler, Parsons, Bourdieu, and Foucault as was discussed above. I have come to realize that the representation of family as a panopticon is a relatively unexamined field and furthermore that the proportion of works that apply a sociological point of view for criticizing the same is even less. Out of *Sons and Lovers* and *The Ordeal of Richard Feverel*, the former has been worked upon by several critics and researchers but the latter has been hardly talked about. Moreover, the former’s research articles have been dominated by psychoanalytic, formalistic, or feminist approaches and maybe some more but have hardly been analysed through the lens of a panopticon.

This research is novel in a way because only psychologists and sociologists have worked upon this topic but very few literary researchers have focussed upon the issue of familial power in countless poems and novels. This research proposes to knit distinct powers of two different parents of different sex and times, taking the role of a panopticon excluding its architectural setup. The Foucauldian approach of panopticon did not include harsh punishments but only a continuous check on prisoners and this approach will surely help in studying the adolescent characters suffering from internalized coercion. Leaving aside parents’ love and genuine care, this study will primarily talk about constructs of power within a family that force adolescent protagonists to just play the role of a puppet. The concept of a parent as a panopticon

does not restrict only to the above-mentioned novels but is prevalent all over the world where overprotective parents act as an impediment in the cognitive and social development of a child.

Along with the Foucauldian approach, I would be also analysing the characters of the novels by using the Orwellian concept i.e. “Big Brother is Watching You” (1). One reads George Orwell’s famous line, “Who controls the past controls the future. Who controls the present controls the past” (313) and wonders how truly it fits not only with political institutions but also with family. In *The Ordeal of Richard Feverel*, Sir Austin plays the role of ‘Big Brother’ who continuously looks at Richard (his son) and governs his life throughout the novel. Even in *Sons and Lovers*, Mrs. Morel monitors her sons’ lives not by watching or investigating about them but by manipulating their thoughts and actions. These approaches suit the research most because the major aim of the study is to trace the concept of domestic power which is very similar to the surveillance strategies developed by Foucault and Orwell.

This study will root out the reasons behind the creation of these vulnerable copies of a domestic panopticon and why are children expected to inherit ages-long identities, occupations, achievements, struggles, and fears of their parents which further must be passed on to the next generation. The research will attempt to seek an answer that why only absolute sovereignty of bourgeoisie over proletariats, white colonizers over black colonized, men over women is wrong while the sovereignty of parent over an adult child is completely justified and is universally accepted. The other purpose of research is to accentuate discrete shades of domestic panopticon woven in the novels of Meredith and Lawrence, the shades which haven’t been commented on much. The study will also draw differences between a father as a panopticon and a mother being the completely different one on the other side.

Analysis

Meredith’s Sir Austin, his son Richard and Lawrence’s Mrs. Morel, her sons William and Paul are the major characters around whom the research will revolve. These two primary texts are prominent examples that talk about parental care that turns into obsession. The very title of these novels tells us about the major theme of novels. In *The Ordeal of Richard Feverel: A History of Father and Son*, Meredith used the word ‘ordeal’ to depict severe tests and trials that Richard had to pass through different stages of his life due to his tyrannic father. On the other hand, the title *Sons and Lovers* makes it clear to comprehend that it deals with children who chaotically switch roles, sons at one time and lovers at the other because of their reserved and sensitive mother. Parental support and their over engagement in a child’s life has always

been considered positive. However, recently the very idea of overly-involved parents has shifted from supportive to over-intrusive. These “helicopter parents” are depicted in novels, music, and popular media as poking entities, constantly lingering over their young adult child in areas of academic studies, decision making, looking for love relationships, and socio-cultural relationships (Shoup, Gonyea, & Kuh, 2009).

The analysis of the parent as a panopticon will be carried out by comparing and contrasting the parent-child relationship of both novels. Here, panopticons not only watch their children’s physical movement and actions but also their mental bearings and exploits. In “The Ordeal” the narrator says, “Richard was neither to go to school nor to college. Sir Austin considered that the schools were corrupt, and maintained that young lads might by parental vigilance be kept pretty secure from the Serpent until Eve sided with him: a period that might be deferred, he said. He had a system of education for his son” (Meredith, ch.1). After reading these lines, readers can easily deduce the ‘powerful system’ of Sir Austin’s home and his views regarding the difficult stages a child has to pass through. Oppositely in *Sons and Lovers* narrator talks about the strong emotional manipulation and expectation of a mother from her two favourite sons. The narrator says, “Now she had two sons in the world [...] [and] these men would work out what she wanted; they were derived from her, they were of her, and their works would also be hers” (Lawrence 116). The two parents get in way of their children’s individual lives and control them according to their views, past fears, appreciations, and disgust regarding society.

The Visible (father) panopticon in *The Ordeal of Richard Feverel*

Big Brother in *Nineteen Eighty-Four* acted as an omnipresent observer and thus affected the behaviour of the observed. Similarly in *The Ordeal of Richard Feverel*, Sir Austin observes his son Richard through the course of his life. The novel was written in the Victorian age and the age was famous for its ethics, norms, and morals. Richard was a child who grew in this Victorian mindset, only in his home under his father and his wise cousin Adrian’s surveillance because of which he had zero experience of the outer world. Sir Austin’s solicitor’s son Ripton was the only comrade of his age. On his fourteenth birthday, he went out with his playfellow Ripton and explored all that he could do for that one day. His father threw a party for his son’s birthday but Richard came home late and didn’t talk to his son. At midnight, he

visited his son's room and eavesdropped on the children's curious discussions about fire, violence, and vengeance.

After listening to these conversations Sir Austin's 'system' was on a verge of breaking. These lines talk much about a father's fear, "To Sir Austin, it seemed as if a gulf had suddenly opened between them. The boy had embarked and was on the waters of life in his own vessel. . . . the dangers were about him, the temptations thick on him, and the devil on board piloting. If a day had done so much, what would years do? Were prayers and all the watchfulness he had expended of no avail?" (Meredith, ch. 4). After that day Sir Austin started investigating his son's actions because "Richard showed symptoms of a disposition to take refuge in lies" (ch. 5). These lies of his son enabled him to observe and provide for the movements of creatures in the dark. He, therefore, treated the boy as he commonly did, he kept an unseen eye upon him and Richard saw no change in his father to make him think he was suspected. (ch. 5). During their mini exploits, Richard played the role of a leader(powerful) while Ripton was the submissive one. The former used to think that he had fooled his father and taught Ripton to defy his parent too but he himself was unaware of the visible panopticon.

Sir Austin wrote in his notebook, "Between Simple Boyhood and Adolescence—The Blossoming Season—on the threshold of Puberty, there is one Unselfish Hour—say, Spiritual Seed-time." (ch.12). He made sure that good seed should be planted in Richard only by his vigilant supervision. He said, "Every act, every fostered inclination, almost every thought, in this Blossoming Season, bears its seed for the Future. The living Tree now requires incessant watchfulness." (ch.12). Richard had to submit all his academic, moral, social, and psychological inputs in front of his father before going to bed. Whole of the family transformed into a prison-house where Sir Austin stood in the middle, playing the role of a panopticon. It is indirectly proven that 'the system' of Sir Austin was quite similar to a panopticon as Meredith writes, "Sir, Austin despite his rigid watch and ward, knew less of his son's emotions, fears, and personal insights. Adrian too inspected Richard and obeyed his duty by telling Austin about his son's inclination towards poetry. Lady Blandish likewise hinted at his mooning propensities. Sir Austin from his lofty watch-tower of the System had foreseen it, he said. But when he came to hear that the youth was writing poetry, his wounded heart had its reasons for being much disturbed" (ch.12).

Austin totally controlled Richard's 'magnetic age', as he says it, the age of violent attractions and dangerous love (ch.13). In order to preserve his son from any visible symptom of passion, people at Raynham were put on their guard by him. He wanted to control the

insatiate appetite of his child. He was in fear that Olympians (Richard) were about to storm the Titans (Sir Austin's System) and he wanted to protect both. When Richard fell in love with Lucy, his father was against it because she was the daughter of a lower-class farmer and he still carried his own marital baggage along with him. There was a time when the son wanted to leave the town and go back to Raynham for his beloved Lucy but his father didn't let him go. He says, "Well, then, my son, 'said the baronet, preserving his half-jocular air, "I must tell you that it is my wish to have you in town. For three weeks Richard had to remain in town and endure the teachings of the System in a new atmosphere" (ch.21-22) In a conversation between Austin and Emmeline (his wife), he says;

"Ah! do not trifle, my friend. Say: would you have had him act as young men in his position generally do to young women beneath them?"

Sir Austin did not like the question. It probed him very severely.

"You mean," he said, "that fathers must fold their arms, and either submit to infamous marriages or have these creatures ruined." (Meredith, ch.33)

These lines clearly reflect Sir Austin's obsession with his paternal duty, a duty to protect his child from his marital match. For that matter, he even brings Lady Judith's character in Richard's life so that he could stay away from Lucy. He tried to control his son's emotions and in process of protecting him, he harmed him unknowingly. The novel comprises of this 'visible' panopticon in the name of 'system'. It is strange that we never really learn a great deal about what this so-called System comprises.

The invisible (Mother) panopticon in *Sons and Lovers*

Mrs. Morel is a mother who is emotionally involved in her sons' lives. In this novel we will never encounter something like 'Sir Austin's System' but there is a panopticon, well-constructed in the minds of children but they are blind to see that as it is invisible. Mrs. Morel felt lonely with her husband which led her to look for her sons' presence all the time. She always suspected her sons' relationship with women. This is her response when a lady calls for William one day, "I don't approve of the girls my son meets at dances. And he is not at home" (Lawrence,65). She had absolute control over her child's decisions. Just because Mr. Morel was a good dancer, she didn't want her son to go the same way as his father. When William got a place in London, 'Her heart began to close and grow dreary with despair. She loved him so much! More than that, she hoped in him so much. Almost she lived by him. She liked to do

things for him..... Now, she would not do it for him. Now he was going away” (67). She raised her four children practically by herself. Although she controlled the whole of her family but this research will solely focus on William and supremely Paul.

Her treatment of Paul was different from that of other children. She started controlling him with the help of her excessive love and care when William left for Nottingham. Mrs. Morel acted as an invisible panopticon only for her sons (especially Paul) and not for her daughter Annie. Their mother has such a significant role in their lives, that both of the sons compare their lovers with their mother. After William’s death, Mrs. Morel’s heart broke into pieces which were joined by her son Paul. Now, she had a strong urge of fulfilling her maternal duty towards Paul, the delicate child. She wanted to shield him from all the attacks and obstacles that life threw at him. As Paul started spending some time with Miriam, the invisible panopticon started off with its task;

“She could feel Paul being drawn away by this girl. And she did not care for Miriam.

"She is one of those who will want to suck a man's soul out till he has none of his own left," she said to herself; "and he is just such a gaby as to let himself be absorbed.

She will never let him become a man; she never will."(Lawrence 178)

She always told Paul that he didn’t have much sense for dealing with girls, love and relationships. With the passage of time, Mrs. Morel asked her son to stop meeting Miriam and he listened to her because of the emotional incest he always experienced with his mother. She hated Miriam for snatching away her innocent son. In a conversation between mother and son, Mrs. Morel says, “It seems to me you like nothing and nobody else. There’s neither Annie, nor me, nor anyone now for you” (Lawrence 233). The mother’s excessive love and care for her son made him dissatisfied with himself and with everything. His mother played the role of a pivot or pole of his life from which he could not escape. Later on, she suspected him leaning towards Clara Dawes but was not dismissive of her as she has been with Miriam because she forced Paul to think more for himself which his mother didn’t approve of. She always thought that Miriam undermined Paul’s joy and blamed her for her son’s distress. But Paul encountered his ‘self’ only in presence of Miriam and never with Clara. Under the spell of her mother (powerful), son (powerless) had to take all of the decisions that she made. While breaking up with Miriam, he himself was unaware of the reason behind it and he says;

"I want us to break off—you be free of me, I free of you."

"And what about these last months?"

"I don't know. I've not told you anything but what I thought was true."

"Then why are you different now?" "I'm not—I'm the same—only I know it's no good'

"You haven't told me why it's no good."

"Because I don't want to go on—and I don't want to marry."(Lawrence 321)

The children never have the power to choose what's best for them because they are inexperienced and are constantly protected from vicious surroundings but they are all alone when there's nobody around. Through the course of the novel, Paul says a number of times, "Why can't I do as I like "(Lawrence 352) but he never gets a satisfactory answer. He breaks off with all of his surroundings and people but his mother. The construction of mother as a panopticon seems disrespectful but Mrs. Morel enjoyed a sovereign status that she played in her sons' lives which made her son Paul, a tragic character.

The Birth and death of the Panopticon

Most of the parents would never accept that at some point in life, they act like a panopticon. They become the custodian of their child's heart and brain. Austin and Gertrude Morel are examples of such parents who transform into a panopticon due to their past fears and falls. Their bad marital relationships forced them to protect their children from the same. On the one hand, Austin didn't want Richard to write poetry because his wife eloped with a passionate poet, on the flip side Mrs. Morel didn't want her sons to dance and date girls because Mr. Morel did the same. He responds to Lady Blandish in this way when he came to hear about Richard writing poems;

"Surely,' said Lady Blandish, "you knew he scribbled?"

"A very different thing from writing poetry," said the baronet. "No Feverel has ever written poetry."

"I don't think it's a sign of degeneracy," the lady remarked. "He rhymes very prettily to me."

'A London phrenologist, and a friendly Oxford Professor of poetry, quieted Sir Austin's fears" (Meredith, ch.12)

Sir Austin's past fears compelled him to guard his son's life and that constant feeling of uneasiness lead him in constructing a safe territory for his son. He was a misogynist because his wife eloped with his best friend. This was the reason behind his taking the form of a

panopticon. Similarly, Mrs. Morel had suffered tremendously due to her failed marriage and while growing up when Paul becomes more critical of his father, Mrs. Morel encourages him to reject his father and she persistently passed on her fears to her sons' minds. While communicating with William regarding his marriage she says, "My boy, remember you're taking your life in your hands," said Mrs. Morel. "Nothing is as bad as a marriage that's a hopeless failure. Mine was bad enough, God knows, and ought to teach you something, but it might have been worse by a long chalk"(148). Paul's actions are always the outcome of his mother's feelings which let her control him as he has never seen the world through his eyes. Mrs. Morel herself didn't know that she was pressurizing her sons to accept her fears and insecurities which eventually dehumanized them. Sir Austin and Mrs. Morel took the form of a panopticon to save their children but they fell victim to their excessive love, care, and paranoia to which there was no escape.

But this panopticon can never remain intact as long as children start loving the safety. Richard, William, and Paul were the children who never cross-questioned their parents regarding the norms of the family but they did try to break it. Adrian tells Sir Austin that, "They've been studying Latude's Escape. I found the book open in Ricky's room, on the top of Jonathan Wild" (ch. 6). Latude was a French writer who was known for his multiple escapes from the prison and Richard loved reading about him as he too wanted to flee his father's 'System'. This was the first step that shattered Sir Austin's (panopticon's) system or structure. In the case of William and Paul, both tried to fly out of their mother's control as they both ran after girls of their ages whom Mrs. Morel didn't approve of. Paul had always listened to his mother's advice and he developed a behaviour of pleasing her but his soul had a deep tenderness for Miriam too. At certain times mother had no right over her son and there was a coldness between him and her. The theme of the rise and fall of the panopticon is prevalent in both novels, the only difference is the type of panopticon, the first being a father (visible) and the second, being the mother (invisible). Both panopticons took birth because of failed marital relationships and both suffered death turning their prisoners into hopeless dependent morons.

Conclusion

The aim of this study was to shoot questions at traditional roles of parental authority. Not much research has been done on children's perception on surveillance, thus making the base upon which this study can stand fairly limited but it tried to accomplish its goals. In these testing times of pandemic, a lot of young adults have been staying back at their homes for two

years which undoubtedly has provided them with a safe environment but home can never be a territory of growth. Home and parents (Shield and Sword respectively) can keep us safe only under their control but the moment this thin film of control is broken, the 'safe child' is exposed to the outer world (battlefield) where he/she stands alone as a miserable warrior.

This research has proven that sheer familial panopticism will be of no profit because post-panopticism will always be tragic. Both of the novels end on a tragic note, in the case of Richard, his ordeal was finally over because he died. In his paternal home, under the roofs of law completely removed from the influence of his conscience, he had always been safe but when he stepped out, the shield vanished, so did he. In the case of Paul, his mother died and he stood alone as a derelict. Towards the end of the novel, Paul says to Miriam, "You love me so much, you want to put me in your pocket. And there I will die smothered." (Lawrence,451). He was so much controlled by his mother's love that he should rather have said these lines to her and not Miriam.

The over-attachment and possessive behaviour of parents converts them into a panopticon, the institutional building or preferably a socializing agency that controls children, their thought process, their hearts, emotions, manners and what not. It has been depicted by most literary texts including the two primary texts of this research that rebellion against a tyrannical "system" of parental education or guidance leads children to a dark tale of sexual betrayal and overwhelming tragedy but this research tried to locate the excessive role of parents in their children's life which is the real reason behind the tragic fall of these adolescent protagonists. This topic grants an extended scope for further research on various families of literature. Among various other kinds of literature, Indian literature is famous for stories of typical Indian parents, households, rules, and that field can also be researched upon by using panopticon's concept. It is necessary to note that parents play a crucial role in their child's life but they must not transmit their past fears and insecurities to their children for they got their individual rises and falls. So, this discipline/system shall never turn into a suffocating grasp for children because they are the 'self' and not the 'other'.

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